

TAKING INTO ACCOUNT INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS OF STUDENTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE

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Abstract. *There are discussed in the article principles of forming for the future teachers skills for personality-oriented education planning. In the article is described necessity of students's individual features consideration in distribution them to groups with the purpose of development of concrete professional competences.*

Keywords: *future teacher, student, personality-oriented educating and education, process of educating, activity, pedagogical masteries, knowledge, abilities and skills, pedagogical practice, pedagogical collaboration.*

Introduction. Today, training future teachers to design a student-centered educational process is of great pedagogical importance. Despite the existence of multifaceted approaches in this area, problems such as the organization and management of the person-centered learning process, improving the content, methods and quality of teaching, preparing it for the implementation of the person-centered learning process remain to be addressed.

When training future teachers to design a person-centered educational process, special attention should be paid to:

- The projected educational process has the potential to develop students, and the future teacher is fully prepared to design and organize this process;
- The project of the educational process corresponds to the conceptual basis of person-centered education;
- The project of the educational process clearly states the areas of activity of the teacher in the organization of the person-centered educational process.

It is expedient to determine whether future teachers have mastered the conceptual foundations of the person-centered learning process using the following: 1. technological; 2. intellectual-valuable; 3. through areas of cognitive activity.

It is advisable for professors to use diagnostic methods to determine the skills of future teachers in each area.

The purpose of such a diagnosis is to determine the level of readiness of teachers for the design and organization of person-centered learning process. The first direction of diagnosis should be aimed at determining the professional and personal qualities of the future teacher, pedagogical skills. Attention will be paid to the following: The types of person-centered learning process are shown.

When a teacher diagnoses the results of a person-centered learning process, it is recommended to follow the following:

1. The learning process can provide an opportunity to develop the student's personality and the teacher's willingness to organize this process.

2. Conformity of the learning process to the conceptual basis of person-centered education.
3. Identify areas of activity of the teacher related to the organization of person-centered learning process.

The teacher's mastery of the conceptual basis of the person-centered learning process can be determined by the following criteria: technological, intellectual-value and areas of cognitive activity. The diagnostic technique is used to determine the scope of activity performed on each parameter. The purpose of such a diagnosis is to determine the level of readiness of teachers for the organization of person-centered learning process [1.28-38.].

Analysis of recent research and publications. The first direction of diagnosis should be aimed at determining the professional personal qualities of the teacher, pedagogical skills. In doing so, attention is paid to the following (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Professional personal qualities of the future teacher, factors determining pedagogical skills

- The teacher's pedagogical thinking is focused on the integrated development of the student's personality;
- positive, creative attitude of the teacher to his pedagogical activity;
- The teacher's desire to improve their pedagogical activity in accordance with the requirements of educational reforms, state educational standards;
- the teacher's desire to overcome obstacles to their professional development. For the same purpose, surveys, questionnaires, questions and answers, observations were conducted with students of the Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers in the field of "Professional Education". A total of 180 students participated in the surveys.

During the observation of the readiness of future teachers to organize a person-centered learning process, a number of specific aspects were identified. This is reflected in the following

social, psychological and pedagogical situations. They were also asked questions aimed at identifying their opportunities to learn the concept of person-centered education. *For example:*

1. What do you mean by a person-centered learning process?
2. How do you envision methods and technologies for organizing a person-centered learning process, and which of them do you apply?
3. How developed are your value orientations?
4. Are you interested in a person-centered learning process?
5. Do you have enough knowledge and experience to organize a person-centered learning process?

6. Do you believe that you will succeed in organizing a person-centered learning process in the future? Attempts were made to observe the readiness of future teachers to organize a person - centered educational process in certain pedagogical situations. The results of the observations are presented in Table 1. Among the study participants, it was found that the indicators of skills in organizing the person-centered learning process were much lower. The fact that future teachers have a valuable attitude to their pedagogical activity is an important condition for the organization of a person-centered educational process. The performance of general secondary schools should be assessed in the same light.

Table 1. The ability of prospective teachers to analyze a person-centered learning situation.

Parts of a person-centered learning situation	High	Average	Lower	Those who find it difficult to answer
The process of learning	18,3	23,3	22,1	36,3
Emotional	20,1	26,1	20,0	33,6
Directional	23,9	15,6	27,2	33,3
Optional	17,2	25,0	24,4	33,4
Readiness to analyze a specific pedagogical situation	18,9	22,2	24,3	34,3

Teachers should always be prepared to develop the student as an individual. The school teaching staff should evaluate the performance of each teacher from this perspective. Successful preparation of the student for social life is one of the main tasks of the person-centered educational process. Today's experience clearly shows that the theoretical knowledge acquired by graduates is not enough for them to find a worthy place in social life. That is why there is a strong need to improve the work of many teachers today.

In order to organize the educational process in a purposeful way, future teachers must have mastered the conceptual foundations of person-centered education. In monitoring the knowledge, skills and abilities of future teachers, professors must adhere to the principles of transparency, humanity, integrity, continuity, fairness, democracy. This requires, first of all, to determine the knowledge of the future teacher in the field of acquisition of vital, professional values. The attitude of future teachers to the design and organization of the person-centered

educational process, their desire to enrich their knowledge and skills in their professional activities, to master the skills of creating pedagogical conditions that are favorable to students in all respects. The needs of future teachers for their professional development play an important role in the design and organization of person-centered educational process. To this end, professors should develop a system of pedagogical measures aimed at ensuring the professional development of future teachers.

Our observations show that many students rate their knowledge higher than their current level of practice. To ensure the effectiveness of professional pedagogical education, teachers must take measures to ensure the effectiveness of the educational process, to be able to resolve conflicts and contradictions with students in a timely manner, to pay special attention to their activities in the pedagogical practice.

This approach creates a comfortable, successful learning and social environment among the students in the group. To do this, professors must constantly improve their professional and pedagogical activities, pay special attention to equipping students with person-centered educational technologies.

Another important aspect that teachers should pay attention to is the identification of students with different levels of training in the field of design and organization of person-centered educational process and the provision of pedagogical assistance and support for the development of their professional competencies. One of the important tasks of our research is to determine the readiness of future teachers to design and organize the educational process aimed at personal development and to provide pedagogical assistance in the development of their competencies in this area.

A number of principles need to be followed in preparing future teachers to design a person-centered educational process. They are:

- Ensuring the constant change and development of the activities of future teachers in the organization of person-centered educational process, the expression of humanity, the priority of values, intellectual stability, creativity, responsibility and the ability to demonstrate their competence;
- Ensuring that future teachers are ready to organize a person-centered educational process, reflected not only in their knowledge and skills, but also in pedagogical practice;
- The assessment of knowledge, skills and abilities of future teachers in the field of designing a person-centered educational process should be relevant not only to the pedagogical task they perform, but also to their professional competencies and behavior.

The results of monitoring the process of higher pedagogical education allowed to determine the model of preparation of future teachers for this activity, who in the future will be the main subject of the person-centered educational process. It was found that students who are prone to mastering reproductive methods tend to work on the basis of materials provided in the curriculum.

Results and discussion

In the process of pedagogical practice, they used a cognitive orientation in teaching students and tried to impart knowledge to students within this direction. We have witnessed them communicate with students without any barriers. It was observed that there was no need to develop their professional competencies, skills and knowledge levels. Such students were found to lack personal initiative and time, limited opportunities, and not having enough objective information

about themselves. We have witnessed that they do not engage in diagnosing students' level of development in a person-centered learning process.

Therefore, it was observed that in students with such experience, the experience of directing the learning process to the student's personality is not sufficiently formed. Students with creative qualities, independent thinking, sought to improve to some extent the forms and methods of their pedagogical activities.

They can express their views on new pedagogical technologies, innovative methods, their level of effectiveness. Such students strive to apply these innovations in their activities in the process of pedagogical practice. At the same time, it was observed that they were not demanding of students. The main reason for this is the lack of confidence in the way students achieve their goals in students with such activity skills. It was observed that the interest in the person-centered educational process arose after seminars, methodical classes, pedagogical trainings.

As a result of observing the lessons of prospective students with a high level of professional competence, it became clear that there was a situation of long-term non-compliance with the lessons learned. They learn ideas, approaches, knowledge and concepts related to the design and organization of a person-centered learning process, mainly through lectures and seminars. However, they do not try to enrich their knowledge and experience in this field on the basis of independent knowledge, research, study.

Creative, self-directed research students stand out from their peers with their sustained need for professional and creative development. They have a valuable, creative approach to pedagogical activity. Such students can establish effective cooperation with science teachers, class teachers in the process of pedagogical practice. They have a strong, sustained interest in the person-centered educational process, and are able to comprehensively analyze their professional competencies, behaviors, attitudes, and creative approaches. It was found that such students were well versed in diagnostic techniques and were able to apply them in their place. They have the ability to act according to the situation in the educational process. However, in such students, in some cases, there is a lack of understanding of those around them, the inability to properly allocate time during the lesson. They value the trust of their classmates and professors, and see such trust as a key factor in motivating them to be creative. The need for personal and professional development was evident in the students who had a high value - creative attitude to their profession. They were found to have the ability to manage themselves morally and emotionally among teachers and the student community when needed. Such students always strive to be leaders in their groups and achieve this.

The main goal of students with such experience is to develop the student's personality and to achieve the expected effectiveness in the person-centered educational process. They have a deep understanding of the conceptual foundations, concepts, technologies of person-centered education and understand the need to rely on them in the educational process.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, it is important to inform students that the professional skills of the teacher are closely linked with a number of modes of personal development of the student. A personal approach to education requires the definition of the conceptual basis, purpose, content and technology of the teacher training process on the basis of new pedagogical thinking.

Active activation of the tasks performed by the person in the educational process, understanding of the existing features of pedagogical activity, directing the learning process to

the student. Research in recent years has focused on a comprehensive study of the conditions of teacher-centered education, the factors that ensure the success of pedagogical activities, the pedagogical situation aimed at the development of the student's personality. The teacher's experience in the field of student personality formation plays an important role in this.

The goal of each teacher aimed at developing the student's personality is achieved in coordination with all other teachers. In this regard, attention should be paid to the formation of the student's personality as a whole. The use of certain technologies in the process of person-centered learning has important social and pedagogical significance. Pedagogical activity aimed at student development requires the establishment of a relationship based on value equality between teachers and students. The concept of personal development mechanism requires working with them as a highly skilled professional. To do this, educational process managers need to work on preparing teachers for pedagogical activities in the new system.

Teachers who organize a person-centered learning process are professionals who promote individual, unique professional experiences. The intellectual and creative activity of the teacher is an important condition for the organization of a person-centered learning process. To do this, they must constantly search and think creatively in the course of their activities. He achieves this as a result of his experience. It depends on the teacher's creativity, responsibility, tendency to analyze situations.

REFERENCES

1. Resolution No. 466 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 07.08.2020 "On approval of normative legal documents regulating the system of continuous primary, secondary and secondary special professional education in the Republic of Uzbekistan". <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/4945840>
2. Абдукаримов Х. Касбий педагогик фаолият. – Т.: «O'qituvchi» НМИУ, 2010.
3. Беспалько В.П., Татур Ю.Г. Системно-методическое обеспечение учебно-воспитательного процесса подготовки специалистов. – М.: «Высшая школа», 1988.
4. Митина Л.М. Личностное и профессиональное развитие человека в новых социальных условиях. // Журнал «Вопросы психологии», М., 1997, № 4. –С. 28-38.
5. Крюкова Е.А. Личностно-развивающие образовательные технологии: природа, проектирование, реализация. – Волгоград: «Перемена», 1999. –С. 196.
6. Ищук В. В. Модель профессиональной подготовки будущих учителей физической культуры на основе контекстного и проектного обучения. // «Молодой ученый», 2014, № 2. –С. 765-769.
7. Z.K.Ismailova, B.R.Muqimov S 2019. The Use of Innovation Technologies in the Formation of Students' Professional Competences. International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT), Hindiston, № 9. P.p. 6907-6911.
8. Z.K.Ismailova, R.K.Choriev S 2019.Peculiarities of professional self-development of a future teacher in the context of personality-oriented pedagogy. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences, Amerika, № 7 (12), P.p. 505-508.
9. Z.K.Ismailova, D.Ximmataliev, B.Ergashev S 2020. Actual problems of continuous professional education of future teachers” (Aktualnye problemy nepreryvnogo professionalnogo obrazovaniya budushchix pedagogov) Jurnal OPCION.ISSN 1012-1587/ISSNe 2477-9385- Maracaibo-Venezuela